

Managing other pests

Control of *Hirschmanniella oryzae* nematodes in rice

A. Singh, Haryana Agricultural University (HAU), Rice Research Station, Kaul; M. R. Dalal and D. S. Bhatti, HAU, Hisar, India

An experimental field infested naturally with 50 *H. oryzae* nematodes, 100 g soil was used to evaluate nematicides in 1987. A section of the field with a uniform nematode population was used as nursery. Pregerminated seeds of rice cultivar Jaya were sown in 10 1- × 1-m beds at 40 g seed/m². Eight plots were treated with nematicides at 1.0 kg ai/ha (two plots each with carbofuran, phorate, diazinon, and MOCAP and two plots

Effect of treatments on yield, fresh weight of roots, panicles/hill, and nematode population of rice in Kaul, India.

Treatment	Plant ht (cm)	Panicles (no./hill)	Total fresh weight (g)	Nematode population (no.) at harvest		Grain yield (t/ha)	Yield increase (%)
				In 2 g roots	In 100 g soil		
Untreated	69.8	6.0	28.2	14.8	41.2	4.4	-
Nursery - carbofuran	77.0	8.6	44.2	6.8	21.2	5.1	15
Nursery - phorate	73.2	8.0	41.9	7.8	25.0	4.9	11
Nursery - diazinon	76.4	7.8	37.8	8.8	28.0	4.8	10
Nursery - MOCAP	73.6	6.8	39.2	8.5	30.5	4.7	7
Nursery + field - carbofuran	79.3	8.9	49.4	4.0	18.8	5.5	25
Nursery + field - phorate	77.7	8.4	47.3	4.5	22.2	5.2	20
Nursery + field - diazinon	77.2	8.2	42.0	5.5	24.5	5.1	16
Nursery + field - MOCAP	77.0	7.0	43.4	5.2	29.8	5.0	13
LSD (0.05)	5.04	0.7	-	1.4	9.6	0.7	

untreated). Seedlings were transplanted 30 d after seeding in 5 × 2-m plots. Half the plots were treated with the same chemicals 50 d after transplanting, in a random block design with four replications.

Yields in all treated plots increased (see table). Significant yield increases were only with carbofuran and phorate treatments in the nursery and in the field. Nematodes/100 g soil at harvest were lowest in these plots. □

Farming systems

Introducing high-yielding rice into a jute cropping system with limited nutrient supply

R. K. Roy and R. C. Choudhary, Jute Research Station, Katihar, Rajendra Agricultural University, Bihar, India

Jute (*Corchorus capsularis* L.) is the most important cash crop in northeastern Bihar. It is mostly grown as a wet season crop. If jute harvest is delayed after mid-Aug, fields are generally left fallow in the wet season.

It has been reported that soil fertility improves after jute, because of the positive rhizosphere, root residues, and leaf-fall.

We studied the possibility of growing short-duration rice variety Pusa 2-21 after jute under limited NPK for 3-yr (1983-85) in different fields. Experimental soil was clay loam with pH 7.2 and medium in fertility (0.06-0.08% available N, 8-10 kg available P/ha, and 125-175 kg available K/ha). Average annual rainfall at Katihar is

Grain yield of rice and net profit with different rates of fertilizer applications. Bihar, India, 1983-85

Fertilizer (kg/ha)	No N		20 kg N/ha		40 kg N/ha		60 kg N/ha		Mean	
	Mean grain yield (t/ha)	Net return (Rs/ha)	Mean grain yield (t/ha)	Net return (Rs/ha)	Mean grain yield (t/ha)	Net return (Rs/ha)	Mean grain yield (t/ha)	Net return (Rs/ha)	Mean grain yield (t/ha)	Net return (Rs/ha)
8.6 P	1.8	1606	2.0	1850	2.2	2155	2.4	2348	2.1	1990
17.2 P	2.1	1957	2.1	1918	2.4	2354	2.4	2448	2.2	2169
Mean	1.9	1782	2.1	1884	2.3	2255	2.4	2398		
8.3 K	1.9	1719	2.1	1888	2.3	2266	2.5	2607	2.2	2120
16.6 K	2.0	1844	2.1	1881	2.3	2243	2.3	2188	2.2	2039
Mean	1.9	1781	2.1	1884	2.3	2254	2.4	2396		
LSD (0.05) (t/ha)	N - 0.2		P - 0.1		N × K 0.2					
(Rs/ha)	(ns)		(ns)		(ns)					

1,360 mm, 13% received in Mar-May and 85% in Jun-Oct. Maximum-minimum temperatures are 40.1-8.6 °C.

A normal jute crop of variety JRC 212 was planted with 40-8.6-16.6 kg NPK/ha.

For rice following jute, four levels of N, two levels of P, and two levels of K (see table) were applied in a randomized complete block design with four replications. All the P and K were applied as basal; N was applied 50% as basal and 50% 2 wk after transplanting. Rice was transplanted

(25-d-old seedlings) the first week of Sep and harvested the last week of Nov.

Yields with 20 kg N/ha were not significantly higher than with no N; yields with 40 and 60 kg N/ha were similar and significantly higher. Yields with 17.2 kg P/ha were superior to those with 8.6 kg P/ha. K could not produce any significant difference in grain yield, but its interaction with N was significant.

Net return/ha did not differ significantly. □